

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TYPES OF COGNITIVE-BEHAVIORAL THERAPIES IN CHILDREN WITH LEARNING DIFFICULTIES

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Abstract

The authors of the present study aim to present a comparative analysis of different forms of cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) in children with learning difficulties. An analytical review of contemporary literature sources in the PubMed and Web of Science databases was conducted. Data are presented on individual CBT, group CBT in the school setting, cognitive-behavioral play therapy, programmes based on parent training, combined parent-child interventions, and computer-based CBT programmes.

Keywords: Cognitive-behavioral therapy, Children, Learning difficulties, Specific learning Disorders, Inclusive education.

Introduction

Learning difficulties/disorders, and more specifically specific learning disorders, affect a significant proportion of school-age children. They are associated not only with lower academic achievement but also with an increased risk of anxiety, depression, behavioral problems and social isolation [7].

Among the most thoroughly studied psychotherapeutic approaches in children and adolescents is cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT). It has proven effectiveness for anxiety disorders, depression, behavioral disorders and chronic stress in the school environment [2,15]. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in adapting CBT for children with learning difficulties, both in clinical and school contexts.

Theoretical foundations of cognitive-behavioral therapy in children

CBT is based on the assumption that thoughts, emotions and behavior are interconnected; changes in cognitive schemas and behavioral patterns lead to a reduction of psychological distress and to more adaptive functioning (Beck, 2011). In children, therapeutic techniques are adapted to developmental characteristics – metaphors, stories, drawings, games, role-plays and behavioral experiments are used.

According to contemporary systematic reviews, CBT in children can be viewed along a continuum from “formal psychotherapy” to “cognitive-behavioral techniques embedded in educational practice”, which are

often implemented by school psychologists and guidance counselors [15].

In children with learning difficulties, CBT aims not only to reduce emotional and behavioral symptoms but also to:

- improve academic motivation and self-esteem;
- manage stress induced by the school environment;
- develop self-regulation skills and executive functions;
- prevent secondary psychopathology (anxiety and depressive disorders, behavioral disorders).

Characteristics and psychosocial needs of children with learning difficulties

Definition and classification

The concept of “learning difficulties” covers a broad spectrum of conditions – from specific learning disorders (dyslexia, dyscalculia, disorders of written expression) through children with intellectual disabilities to children with chronic diseases and behavioral problems that lead to significant difficulties in the learning process [6].

In international classifications (DSM-5, ICD-11), specific learning disorders are defined as academic achievement in at least one area significantly below what is expected, which cannot be explained by intellectual disability, sensory impairments or inadequate schooling.

Comorbidity and mental health

Studies show a strong association between learning difficulties and behavioral/emotional problems – particularly externalizing behavior (aggression, hyperactivity) and attention deficits [7]. Children with learning difficulties often develop:

- low self-esteem and a sense of incompetence;
- avoidance of school tasks;
- secondary anxiety (fear of failure, test anxiety);
- depressive symptoms and social withdrawal.

A group with such characteristics is highly suitable for CBT interventions targeting cognitive distortions (e.g. “I am stupid”, “I will never succeed”) and avoidance behaviors (procrastination, refusal to do homework, truancy).

Aim

The present study aims to provide a comparative analysis of different forms of cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) in children with learning difficulties on the basis of an analytical literature review.

To achieve this aim, we set the following objectives:

- To outline the characteristics of the group “children with learning difficulties” and their specific psychosocial needs.
- To present the main types of CBT interventions applied in this group of children.

Methods: literature review

A targeted review of articles in English was carried out in the PubMed and Web of Science databases (2010–2025), using the keywords “cognitive-behavioral therapy”, “children”, “learning disabilities”, “specific learning disorder”, “school-based CBT”, “parent training”, “play therapy”. More recent publications up to 2025 identified via snowballing through reference lists were also included.

The review covered:

- randomized controlled trials (RCTs);
- quasi-experimental and pilot studies;
- systematic reviews and meta-analyses;
- articles focusing on school-based interventions and the role of school psychologists.

The present article is an analytical review.

Analysis of the results

Comparative analysis of types of cognitive-behavioral interventions in children with learning difficulties

Individual cognitive-behavioral therapy is most often used in children with learning difficulties to:

- reduce anxiety and emotional disorders;
- improve attention and executive functions;
- address academic stress and burnout.

The results of a randomized controlled trial by Molaie (2024) show that 10 sessions of individual CBT (90 minutes each over 5 weeks) in children aged 9–12 years with learning difficulties significantly improve emotional processing and selective attention compared to a control group without intervention [12].

Similar results are observed in CBT programmes targeting academic burnout and related emotional problems. Onuorah, Aneke and Eseadi (2025) report that a

16-session CBT protocol significantly reduces academic burnout in gifted students with learning difficulties, with the effect being sustained over time [13].

The advantages of this type of therapy include: a high degree of individualization; the possibility to integrate specific academic tasks; and work on personal history and self-esteem.

The limitations of individual therapy are: it is resource-intensive (requires time and trained therapists); it is more difficult to scale in the school environment; it includes parents and teachers to a more limited extent, unless explicitly planned.

Group CBT in the school setting

Group school-based programmes combine CBT techniques with group dynamics and are often aimed at:

- academic stress and test anxiety;
- classroom behavior and aggression;
- problem-solving and social skills.

A meta-analysis of school-based cognitive-behavioral interventions shows a significant reduction in aggressive behavior and improvement in psychosocial functioning in students with various difficulties, including learning difficulties [2].

A recent study by Khurana (2025) on a school CBT programme for academic stress and anxiety in adolescents shows that a group intervention delivered by school staff leads to a reduction in stress and an increase in self-efficacy [8]. Although not all participants are diagnosed with learning disorders, the data are relevant for students with academic difficulties.

The advantages of this type of therapy include: high effectiveness with moderate resources – one group includes 6–10 children; natural integration into the school environment; and the possibility for normalization (“I am not alone in my difficulties”) and group support.

The limitations of group CBT are: less individualization; the need to coordinate with the school timetable; and the fact that the effect may vary depending on the quality of facilitation (teacher vs. psychologist).

Cognitive-behavioral play therapy (CBPT)

Cognitive-behavioral play therapy (CBPT) combines CBT principles with playful, symbolic and expressive methods that are suitable for preschool and early school-age children.

Azizi (2020), in a randomized controlled trial, shows that CBPT improves sustained attention in children with specific learning disorders, although the effect on working and short-term memory is not significant [1].

Other studies demonstrate that cognitive-behavioral play therapy reduces social anxiety and increases academic self-efficacy in students with learning difficulties (e.g. pilot RCTs published after 2023).

The advantages of this type of therapy include: high engagement of younger children; the possibility for indirect work on cognitions through play and metaphor; and good potential for integration into resource centers and therapeutic rooms in schools.

The limitations of CBPT are related to: the need for specialized training of therapists; a more limited evidence base compared to classical CBT in older children; and difficulties in standardizing protocols.

Programmes based on parent training (Behavioral Parent Training, CBT-informed)

Parent training based on behavioral and cognitive-behavioral principles is particularly important for children with learning difficulties and comorbid behavioral problems (e.g. ADHD, oppositional behavior).

Large meta-analyses of parent training show moderate to large effects on the reduction of antisocial behavior and improvement of parenting practices [3], cited in Matthys [11]. CBT-informed parent programmes teach parents to apply techniques such as:

- positive reinforcement;
- structured routines;
- consistent consequences;
- cognitive restructuring of negative parental beliefs (“the child is lazy”, “the child will never cope”) [4,5,17].

Based on studies in children with ADHD and learning difficulties, it is concluded that parent training can also indirectly improve academic functioning – by reducing conflicts and increasing engagement with school tasks [14].

The advantages of this type of intervention include: an impact on the child’s primary environment – the home; the possibility for long-term changes in family dynamics; and good compatibility with school-based interventions.

The limitations of parent training are: it requires motivation and stability on the part of parents; it has a weaker direct effect on specific academic skills; and cultural barriers (stereotypes about parental “guilt”, stigma).

Combined parent–child CBT programmes

Combined programmes (e.g. Combined Parent–Child CBT) address both the child’s cognitive-behavioral deficits and parental patterns. Protocols such as CPC-CBT include joint parent–child sessions to develop skills for emotional regulation and positive communication.

According to Lebowitz et al. (2019), a purely parent-based approach aimed at reducing parental accommodation can be as effective as direct child CBT in anxiety disorders [9]. This raises the question of the potential of similar models in children with learning difficulties – especially when direct CBT is hampered by cognitive deficits.

The advantages of this type of therapy include: a synergistic effect – change in both the child and the parent; natural transfer of new skills into everyday life; and potential for more sustainable outcomes.

The limitations of combined programmes are related to: even greater resource and organizational complexity; and fewer available studies focused specifically on learning difficulties.

Computer- and internet-based cognitive-behavioral programmes

In recent years, computer-based cognitive and cognitive-behavioral programmes for children with learning difficulties have been developed, targeting attention, working memory and cognitive flexibility.

A study by Looney (2024) shows that two computer-based cognitive training programmes (CCT) im-

prove working memory, cognitive flexibility and processing speed in students from grades 3 to 6 with different learning difficulties, and demonstrates a model for integrating such interventions into the school day without interrupting curricular content [10].

Although these programmes are more akin to cognitive training than pure CBT, they are often combined with CBT techniques for motivation, self-monitoring and stress management.

The advantages of this type of intervention include: high potential for scalability in the school environment; attractiveness for children; and the possibility for remote delivery.

The limitations are: the need for technological resources and support; the risk of reducing the therapeutic process to “computer games” if not integrated into a broader psychosocial approach; and a limited evidence base for specific learning disorders.

Conclusion

Cognitive-behavioral therapies represent a flexible and evidence-based approach for working with children with learning difficulties. Based on the review of available international data, we arrive at the following conclusions:

- individual CBT is particularly effective for emotional and stress-related problems;
- group school-based programmes have strong preventive potential and are suitable for large-scale implementation;
- cognitive-behavioral play therapy is promising for younger children;
- parent-based and combined programmes ensure sustainable changes at the family-system level;
- digital and computer-based interventions can broaden access to support.

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